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The hidden costs of excluding rejecters in intergroup interventions: How plausibility moderates the effects of introducing multiple social identities

Short title: *PLAUSIBILITY OF INTERGROUP INTERVENTIONS*

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Abstract

Recent studies showed that intergroup interventions should be tailored for groups with specific ideological profile and social contexts, so that they satisfy the target groups' needs. Additionally, some individuals might negatively react to interventions in terms of rejecting their content as untrue. In the experimental context, they can be excluded from the analyses, making the interventions' impact on them unknown. We argue that individuals who are already prejudiced are more likely to assess interventions as implausible. Across five experiments (N = 1896) in post-conflict ex-Yugoslavia, we first explored the predictors of plausibility assessment of two differently framed types of the Gateway group intervention: outgroup- and ingroup-perspective ones; we then tested whether plausibility moderates the interventions' effect on intergroup bias. Our results confirmed that those who perceive the outgroup as more threatening, and who are less prone to perspective taking, are also more likely to reject the intervention framed from the outgroup perspective. Furthermore, not only was this intervention successful for those who accepted its content, but it also backfired for those who rejected it. This calls for re-examining the practices of how interventions are experimentally tested, as well as the way their effects are generalized across populations.

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Introduction

In divided societies, where the relations between ethnic, national, or religious groups are tense, learning about outgroup members' benevolence or positive aspects of their social identity may promote more positive intergroup attitudes. For example, learning that ethnic minority members strongly identify both with their ethnic group and the country they live in, can bridge the gap between the ethnic majority and minority (Levy et al., 2017; Authors, 2019; 2022). Similarly, when ethnic majority members learn that most of their ingroup members perceive the ethnic minority as similar to them can increase their positive feelings towards the minority (Đorđević, 2020). Such information about the outgroup social identities can be used in intergroup interventions to redefine the existing social categorization, consequently reducing intergroup bias (Authors, 2019; 2022; Đorđević, 2020; Levy et al., 2017, 2023).

To attribute the bias reduction to particular psychological mechanisms, it is necessary to test whether the manipulation evoked it, as well as to confirm that the participants understand and believe the intervention content they were exposed to. Whilst manipulation checks (whether the intervention evoked a proposed psychological process) are frequently used as a part of interventions testing (Chester & Lasko, 2021; Fiedler et al., 2021), plausibility and comprehension checks are used relatively rarely in intergroup research (Authors, in preparation). Importantly, if used, they often serve as the exclusion criteria: participants who fail to understand or believe the intervention content are excluded from the analyses of intervention effects (Authors, in preparation). That leaves the intervention to be tested only on the subsample of participants who accepted their content as plausible. The effects on those who rejected the content as implausible thus remain unknown. Additionally, not applying plausibility checks leaves us without any information on participants' perception of the content, further blurring the

mechanisms of intervention instead of clarifying them. Both practices — using plausibility checks as exclusion criteria or not applying them at all — seem to lower generalizability of intervention effects. For example, individuals who disregard intervention content as implausible could be the most prejudiced ones, yet there is no empirical evidence to confirm it. If this is true, it would mean that some interventions are only effective for individuals who do not hold strong outgroup bias, which is especially relevant in (post-)conflict settings. Moreover, the way they affect strongly prejudiced individuals remains unknown, although the real-world application of interventions would necessarily affect a wide audience regardless of their degree of outgroup bias. In line with this, there is evidence that certain interventions are more effective than others to particular socio-demographic or ideological groups or more suitable in one context but not the other (Hameiri et al., 2016; Nir & Halperin, 2025).

In this paper, we explore whether individuals with a particular ideological and attitudinal profile are more likely to reject the intervention portraying dual identification as implausible. We further compare two differently framed dual-identity interventions (Levy et al., 2017) in terms of their plausibility and effectiveness. Finally, we explore the role of plausibility assessment in the two interventions' success in reducing intergroup bias.

Plausibility of intergroup interventions and generalizability of their effects

Plausibility assessment of intergroup interventions is tightly related to replicability and generalizability of their effects. While the research community responded to the replication crisis with a set of recommendations for researchers (Crüwell et al., 2019; Nosek et al., 2022), generalizability and applicability of the experimental effects might be more difficult to operationalize. More precisely, it seems to be difficult to balance between searching for universalities in humans' psychological life and recognizing context-related specificities that modify

how these universalities manifest. Recent analyses and reviews addressed this issue, pointing out that the interventions should be tested more thoroughly in terms of social contexts and characteristics of the target population. They indicated that the researchers should be more careful regarding their participants' beliefs and social background (Bar-Tal & Hameiri, 2020; Čehajić-Clancy & Halperin, 2024) and pointed out that the interventions should be cross-culturally validated (Čehajić-Clancy & Halperin, 2024; IJzerman et al., 2020). Thus, instead of adopting earlier practices of excluding participants who fail to understand or believe the intervention (Authors, 2022a; 2022b; Kunst et al., 2019; Levy et al., 2017), we should understand whether interventions are effective on all subpopulations and, if not, what renders them ineffective.

Although it might seem paradoxical, taking individual differences into account, rather than trying to eliminate them, might help us develop effective psychological intergroup interventions. An intervention's overall effect on intergroup bias can appear weak, yet analyses that account for individual-level variables (e.g., ideology) often reveal substantial heterogeneity: the same intervention may be highly effective for some groups and ineffective for others (Hameiri et al., 2016; Nir & Halperin, 2025). Thus, researchers increasingly advocate for tailored interventions that consider both individual differences and the broader social context in which they are implemented (see Hebel-Sela et al., 2025, for a review). Such approaches rest on the assumption that interventions must align with the psychological needs of the target group, or at least avoid triggering defensive reactions, because prior beliefs may lead prejudiced individuals to dismiss incongruent content (Maier & Richter, 2013).

In particular, individuals who already hold negative outgroup attitudes or are unwilling to adopt the outgroup's perspective may reject the intervention outright, fail to engage with its content, and thus remain excluded from analyses of its effects.

Motivated reasoning and plausibility of intergroup interventions

Why do individuals perceive interventions as implausible when their content conflicts with preexisting worldviews? This may reflect a form of *motivated reasoning*, i.e. individuals evaluating information so that they align with their preexisting values, beliefs, or attitudes. (Ellis, 2022; Kunda, 1990). For example, portraying outgroup members positively might trigger motivated reasoning in highly prejudiced individuals: since a positive description of outgroup members does not fit into their worldview, they reject it as implausible.

Political-psychological research provides the evidence of rejecting outgroup-related information due to motivated reasoning. Individuals would find poll results (Kuru et al., 2017) and scientific evidence (Bayes & Druckman, 2021) less credible if they do not align their beliefs about the addressed issue. Moreover, racially prejudiced Whites are likely to reject factual data about the history of racial oppression and are more prone to accept the untrue information about positive discrimination of the Black people (Feldman & Huddy, 2018).

Applied to intergroup interventions, this principle suggests that ethnically prejudiced individuals are likely to reject affirmative portrayals of ethnic outgroups. Majority members who perceive a minority as threatening may resist evidence of their simultaneous identification with minority ethnicity and country they live in. This resistance could be particularly pronounced in (post-)conflict societies, where identities are politicized and essentialized, anchoring the information processing in societal conflict narratives rather than facts (Authors, 2017; Bar-Tal, 2007; Turjačanin, Dušanić, Lakić, et al., 2017). There is even initial evidence that credibility of

the vignettes used as experimental manipulations can be related to outgroup attitude (Al-Amine & Çakmak, 2025). Therefore, if we use plausibility checks to exclude participants, we cannot know the ideological and attitudinal profile of the excluded ones and how the intervention would affect them. More precisely, we might exclude the very individuals whose attitudes we want to change. This calls for more in-depth empirical research on the relations between individual beliefs and interventions' plausibility assessment, as well as on the way plausibility assessment is related to intervention effects on intergroup bias.

Current study

Given that the assessment of intergroup interventions' plausibility may be shaped by motivated reasoning, and that, to our knowledge, this issue has not been empirically examined, we aimed to disentangle the relationship between (a) individuals' ideological and attitudinal profile, (b) the extent to which they assess the intervention as plausible, and (c) the intervention effectiveness in inducing dual identity perception and consequently reducing intergroup bias. Across five experiments in the post-conflict context of former Yugoslavia, we adopted two types of intervention drawn from the Gateway group paradigm (Levy et al., 2017) and tested them in the context of relation between Serbs and Bosniaks.

Societal context of the present research

During the 1990s violent Bosnian war was fought between Serbs, Bosniaks, and Croats in today's Bosnia and Herzegovina. Here we focus on Serbs and Bosniaks who today live in two sovereign states: Serbia, that supported ethnic Serbian troops in BH, but did not have any war occurrences on its territory¹, and Bosnia and Herzegovina (BH) that was devastated by the war.

¹ Other conflicts during the dissolution of Yugoslavia did occur partially on the Serbian territory, but the Bosnian war took place exclusively on the territory of contemporary Bosnia and Herzegovina.

In 1995 BH was divided along ethnic boundaries into two entities: Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (FBH) where Bosniaks are a majority, and Republika Srpska (RS) with predominantly ethnic Serbian population. In Serbia, ethnic Serbs are a majority, whilst Bosniaks are recognized as a constitutive national minority (Figure 1).

Thirty years later, BH remains a prototypical example of a deeply divided society, with little to none interethnic contact (Pečković, 2017). Whilst Bosniaks are tied to BH and their *Bosnian* (citizens of Bosnia) identity, Serbs are more tied to Serbia as their motherland (Turjačanin, Dušanić, & Lakić, 2017). On the other hand, Serbia recognizes Bosniaks as a national minority with granted cultural and educational autonomy; however, dominant narratives there boost the perception of intergroup threat by promoting competitive victimhood (Obradović, 2016). Thus, status of the two groups in both countries, as well as their different ties to ethnicity and nation, make this context a perfect case-study example for testing how subtle differences in intergroup interventions can make a difference in intervention content plausibility, and further in interventions' effectiveness.

[Figure 1 here]

Gateway group paradigm

The main premise of this paradigm is that a group portrayed as having a complex social identity (e.g., Bosniaks from Serbia identifying as ethnic Bosniaks and Serbian citizens) can bridge the gap between the groups embedded within their complex identity (Serbs and Bosniaks). It proposes that majority members (Serbs) would identify with the gateway group (Bosniaks from Serbia) due to the partially shared social identification. This would, in turn, elicit a positive perception of the gateway group (GG) as a partial ingroup, which should be generalized to the outgroup (Bosniaks) as a whole.

In this paradigm, majority group members are typically presented with vignettes depicting the social world whose effectiveness hinges on perceived plausibility. It also allows us to test two interventions that are directly comparable in terms of outcomes and the proposed mechanism (perceiving GG's dual identity), yet relying on different signals that may vary in plausibility across individuals. For example, an intervention cites an ostensible research report in which GG strongly identifies with both the ingroup (e.g. Bosniak ethnicity) and the outgroup (e.g. Serbian nationality; Authors, 2019). This framing requires participants to be willing to take the outgroup's perspective to perceive the content as plausible. Highly prejudiced individuals, particularly in threat-laden contexts, may find this particularly difficult and thus dismiss the content as implausible. Alternatively, dual identification can be signalled through an ostensible research where the majority group sees the minority as dually identified: the intervention thus relies on an ingroup descriptive norm rather than outgroup self-perception. For participants who distrust the outgroup, this ingroup-based framing may enhance plausibility (see Đorđević, 2020).

Existing evidence indicates that these interventions are effective in post-conflict settings (Authors, 2019; 2022; Đorđević, 2020; Levy et al., 2017; 2023). Moreover, they are not overly resource-intensive, making it feasible to conduct multiple experiments.

Research aims

In this study, we experimentally compared the two types of gateway group intervention (*Outgroup experience intervention*, framed from the outgroup perspective, and *Ingroup norm intervention*, framed as a descriptive ingroup norm) in terms of their plausibility and potential to induce dual identity perception (Experiments 1-3), and their effectiveness in intergroup bias reduction (Experiments 4-5). To address potential motivated reasoning in plausibility assessment, we registered participants' ideology, outgroup threat perception, perspective-taking,

and ingroup identification, and explored their relations to plausibility assessment (Experiments 1-3). The experiments were conducted in Serbia (Experiments 1 and 4), Republika Srpska (Experiment 2), and Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Experiments 3 and 5) with the ethnic majority group members as participants and the relevant minority (Bosniaks or Serbs) as a target group (Fig. 1).

Hypotheses

To our knowledge, predictors of plausibility of intergroup interventions, and the role of plausibility in interventions' effectiveness were not studied before. However, we specified five hypotheses for the experiments 1-3. We expected that the two intervention types (Outgroup experience and Ingroup norm) would, on average, be assessed as equally plausible (H1) and that both would equally impact the perception of the gateway group's dual identity (H2). We also expected dual identity perception to be higher in both Outgroup experience (H3a) and Ingroup norm condition (H3b) compared to the control condition.

Further, we expected ideology to be correlated with both interventions' plausibility: more conservative participants would be less likely to assess them as plausible (H4a). Since strong ingroup identifiers are more likely to stick to ingroup norms (Livingstone et al., 2011), we expected positive relation between ingroup identification and Ingroup norm intervention plausibility (H4b). We also expected positive relation between perspective taking and Outgroup experience intervention plausibility (H4c), i.e., that participants more prone to perspective taking would be more likely to understand outgroup members' feelings (Wang et al., 2003), and therefore believe them. Given that perceived threat typically weakens intergroup trust (Schmid et al., 2014) we expected negative relation between outgroup threat perception and Outgroup

experience intervention plausibility (H4d). Finally, we expected positive correlation between both interventions' plausibility and dual identity perception (H5).

In experiments 4 and 5, we expected both interventions to reduce outgroup bias, i.e., to reduce social distance (H6a), increase positive outgroup feelings (H6b), and increase reconciliation intentions (H6c) compared to control condition. Moreover, drawing from the results of Experiments 1-3, we expected plausibility assessment to moderate this effect: the relation between plausibility and intergroup bias (computed as a principal component of the three measures of bias) would be stronger after the Outgroup experience intervention compared to the Ingroup norm intervention (H7).

Data and code, as well as Supplementary online materials for all five experiments, are available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18848746>. All experiments were ethically approved by the [BLINDED FOR A REVIEW] IRB.

Experiments 1-3

Method

Design and procedure

We used a single factor between-subject design with three conditions: Outgroup experience, Ingroup norm, and Control condition. After signing the informed consent form, participants were first asked to fill in the scales measuring their beliefs. They were then randomly assigned to either Ingroup norm, Outgroup experience, or Control condition. After reading the ostensible research reports (Appendix A), they assessed its plausibility (6-point scale, see Supplementary online materials [SOM], Section 1). Finally, they indicated to what extent they find the GG identified with a) their ingroup (Serbs/Bosniaks) and b) their outgroup

(Bosniaks/Serbs) on a 101-point visual analogue scale. We computed their dual identity perception so that higher scores indicated stronger perceived identification with both groups (SOM, Section 1). The procedure is illustrated in Figure 2.

[Figure 2 here]

All measures used the 7-point Likert scale, except when stated otherwise.

Ideology was measured using a single bipolar item (1 - *extremely left* to 11 - *extremely right*). To make sure that participants considered political orientation in terms of values, we specified what left and right represent and asked them to self-position on social and economic ideological axes. The latter was not used in further analyses.

Ingroup identification was registered using three items adapted from (Authors, 2020), e.g., ‘Being Serb [Bosniak] is an important part of my identity’. Higher scores indicated stronger ingroup identification.

Perspective taking was registered with four items adapted from the Perspective taking subscale of Wang and colleagues’ (2003) Scale of ethnocultural empathy (e.g., ‘It is easy for me to understand what it would be like to be a person of another ethnicity’). Higher scores indicated higher perspective taking.

Outgroup threat perception was measured using the scales constructed after the Intergroup threat theory (Stephan et al., 2015). In Experiment 1, the scale consisted of nine items, four of them capturing realistic threat perception, whilst five items captured symbolic threat perception. In Experiments 2 and 3, we used the 6-item scale, also derived after the Intergroup threat theory (Stephan et al., 2015). Across the contexts, all items loaded on the first principal component (SOM, Section 2), so we used a mean score of threat perception. Higher scores indicated stronger outgroup threat perception.

Outgroup contact was assessed only in Experiments 2-3 and it served as control. On a 5-point scale, participants responded about the frequency of outgroup contact in different situations. Higher scores indicated more frequent outgroup contact.

One attention check item ('This is attention check. Please select value 2.') was included in the Outgroup threat perception scale. Participants who failed to answer it correctly were automatically filtered out.

Participants

We aimed to recruit at least 300 participants in each experiment ($n = 100$ per condition), which would allow us to detect small to medium effect size (Cohen's $f = .18$) with power of .80 and alpha error probability of .05. The overview of samples in Experiments 1-3 is detailed in Table 1.

[Table 1 here]

Analytic strategy

The main analytic strategy is detailed in Table 2. Although testing interactions between the experimental condition and each individual difference variable would give us a better insight into the role of individual differences in plausibility assessment, testing multiple moderators without knowing the predicted shape of interaction would require a sample size way larger than we had resources to collect. Thus, given that this is the first study to examine the relation between beliefs and plausibility of intergroup interventions, we opted for using Pearson correlations. Furthermore, to test the unique contribution of these individual differences, we tested regression models using plausibility as a criterion (see Table 2). Finally, we explored the

moderating effect of plausibility on the relation between experimental condition and dual identity perception, using multiple linear regression (Table 2).

[Table 2 here]

Results

Descriptive statistics and intercorrelations for all three experiments are detailed in Appendix B, Tables B1-B3.

Experiment 1

Hypotheses testing

Contrary to H1 which did not expect differences between two experimental groups, Outgroup experience intervention was, on average, assessed as more plausible ($t(325) = 2.642$, Cohen's $d = .37$; see Table 3). The two interventions did not differ in their potential to induce dual identity perception ($t(325) = 1.731$, $p = .084$, Cohen's $d = .23$; Table 3), supporting H2. Furthermore, in line with H3a and H3b, dual identity perception was higher after the exposure to the Ingroup norm ($t(325) = 4.291$, $p < .001$, Cohen's $d = .58$) and Outgroup experience intervention ($t(325) = 5.856$, $p < .001$, Cohen's $d = .80$).

[Table 3 here]

Ideology was related to plausibility of the Outgroup experience ($r = -.24$, $p = .02$), but not of the Ingroup norm intervention ($r = .04$, $p = .65$), partially supporting H4a. In line with H4b, we observed a positive correlation between plausibility of the Ingroup norm intervention and Ingroup identification ($r = .22$, $p = .018$). Further, Outgroup experience intervention was positively correlated to Perspective taking ($r = .31$, $p < .001$), and negatively to Threat perception

($r = -.49, p < .001$), thus supporting H4c and H4d. Multiple linear regression suggested that, on average, Threat perception was the strongest predictor of plausibility assessment (see Appendix C, Table C1). In line with H5, dual identity perception was positively correlated with plausibility of the Ingroup norm ($r = .32, p < .001$) and Outgroup experience intervention ($r = .61, p < .001$).

Exploratory analysis

We further tested the interaction between perceived plausibility and intervention type in shaping dual identity perception. The regression model explained 38.2% of the variance ($F(13,314) = 16.55, p < .001, R^2_{adj} = .382$). The intervention type * plausibility interactions were below the significance level (outgroup vs. ingroup: $\beta = -.129, p = .062$; outgroup vs. control: $\beta = -.135, p = .051$), but with a trend of stronger relationship between plausibility and dual identity perception in the Outgroup experience condition compared to the Ingroup norm one (Figure 3). This relationship was also stronger in the Outgroup experience condition than in the control. The regression coefficients are detailed in Appendix C, Table C2.

[Figure 3 here]

Experiment 2

Hypotheses testing

Contrary to H1, the content of Ingroup norm intervention was more plausible than the Outgroup experience one ($t(384) = 3.683, p < .001$, Cohen's $d = .47$; see Table 4). In line with H2, there was no difference between the two conditions in their effectiveness in dual identity perception induction ($t(384) = -1.352, p = .177$, Cohen's $d = -.17$; see Table 4). Contrary to H3a, dual identity perception did not differ Ingroup norm and control condition ($t(384) = 1.433, p = .153$, Cohen's $d = .18$). On the other hand, in line with H3b, Outgroup experience intervention

induced stronger dual identity perception compared to the control ($t(384) = 2.810, p = .005$, Cohen's $d = .35$).

[Table 4 here]

Similar to the Experiment 1, ideology was related only to plausibility of the Outgroup experience ($r = -.24, p = .005$), but not of the Ingroup norm intervention ($r = -.10, p = .259$), partially supporting H4a. Contrary to H4b, plausibility of the Ingroup norm intervention was unrelated to ingroup identification ($r = .06, p = .483$). We again found evidence for the correlations between plausibility of the Outgroup experience intervention and Perspective taking ($r = .373, p < .001$), as well as Threat perception ($r = -.25, p = .005$), corroborating H4c and H4d. Linear regression indicated that Outgroup threat was again the strongest predictor of plausibility (Appendix C, Table C3). Finally, plausibility and dual identity perception were positively correlated in both Ingroup norm ($r = .45, p < .001$) and Outgroup experience condition ($r = .63, p < .001$), supporting H5.

Exploratory analysis

As in Experiment 1, we explored the interaction between plausibility and experimental condition on dual identity perception. The model explained 27.3% of the variance ($F(14,372) = 11.36, p < .001, R^2_{adj} = .273$). The interaction between experimental condition and plausibility was significant for the differences between the Outgroup experience intervention and control group ($\beta = -.29, p < .001$), but not for the differences between the two intervention types ($\beta = -.06, p = .356$; Appendix C, Table C4). However, as shown in Figure 4, dual identity perception significantly differed between all levels of assessed plausibility

of the Outgroup experience intervention. The pattern was similar in the Ingroup norm condition, however, the differences were only found between low and high plausibility.

[Figure 4 here]

Experiment 3

Hypotheses testing

In line with H1, the two interventions did not differ regarding their assessed plausibility ($t(390) = 0.026, p = .979$, Cohen's $d = .00$; see Table 5). We also found no difference between the two conditions in their effectiveness in dual identity perception induction ($t(390) = 0.478, p = .633$, Cohen's $d = .06$), supporting H2. Contrary to H3a and H3b, we did not observe the difference in dual identity perception between the control condition and either Ingroup norm ($t(390) = 0.703, p = .482$, Cohen's $d = .08$), or Outgroup experience condition ($t(390) = 1.199, p = .231$, Cohen's $d = .15$).

[Table 5 here]

Unlike Experiments 1 and 2, ideology was unrelated to plausibility of the Outgroup experience ($r = -.05, p = .528$) and Ingroup norm intervention ($r = -.13, p = .140$), which contrasts H4a. Contrary to the results of the Experiment 1, and to H4b, but in line with the Experiment 2, plausibility of the Ingroup norm condition was unrelated to ingroup identification ($r = -.16, p = .067$). In line with H4c and H4d, we again found evidence for the correlations between plausibility of the Outgroup experience intervention and Perspective taking ($r = .25, p = .003$), as well as Threat perception ($r = -.23, p = .007$), confirming our H4c and H4d. Again, Outgroup threat perception was the strongest predictor of plausibility assessment (see Appendix C, Table C5).

Finally, we H5 was supported by positive correlations between dual identity perception and the plausibility of the Ingroup norm intervention ($r = .39, p < .001$), of the Outgroup experience intervention ($r = .40, p < .001$).

Exploratory analysis

Following the principle from the Experiments 1 and 2, we explored the effects of interaction between plausibility and experimental condition on dual identity perception. The model explained 22.6% of the variance ($F(14,378) = 9.195, p < .001, R^2_{adj} = .226$). Similar to Experiment 2, the interaction between experimental condition and plausibility was significant for the differences between the Outgroup experience intervention and control group ($\beta = -.19, p = .015$), but not for the differences between the two intervention types ($\beta = -.07, p = .347$; Appendix C, Table C6). Again, we observed the differences in dual identity perception between different plausibility levels of the Outgroup experience, but of the Ingroup norm intervention intervention (Figure 5).

[Figure 5 here]

Discussion Experiments 1-3

Across these experiments, we tested the plausibility of the two types of Gateway group interventions, as well as their effectiveness in inducing perception of the GG's dual identity. We observed that the context determined which of the intervention types would be assessed as more plausible. Furthermore, although the interventions did not differ within each context in their effectiveness to induce dual identity perception, mean dual identity perception varied from over 50 in Experiment 1 (Serbia) to less than 40 in Experiment 2 (Republika Srpska). Dual identity perception seems sensitive to the history of conflict and current power distribution.

Across three contexts, perspective taking and outgroup threat perception were consistently related to plausibility of Outgroup norm intervention, supporting our assumptions about motivated reasoning in plausibility assessment. Finally, plausibility of the two intervention types was consistently positively related to dual identity perception. That is, the more plausible an intervention was assessed, the more effective it was. Moreover, when controlling for the demographics, intergroup contact, ideology, and intergroup beliefs, effectiveness of the Outgroup experience intervention was more related to plausibility than the Ingroup norm intervention.

The observed patterns suggest that 1) plausibility is determined both by the intervention content AND individuals' beliefs, and 2) plausibility assessment plays a significant role in interventions' effectiveness. The latter is especially true for the intervention portrayed from the outgroup perspective, where it is required from the participants to trust the statements coming from the gateway group members. Therefore, in the Experiments 4 and 5, we tested whether plausibility moderated the way the two types of the Gateway intervention affects bias towards the outgroup. The experiments were conducted in Serbia and FBH, given that the patterns of the results in RS and FBH were almost the same.

Experiments 4-5

Method

Design and procedure

We used the same design and procedure as in Experiments 1-3. In addition, after answering about dual identity perception, participants filled in the measures of intergroup bias

(Outgroup feelings, Social distance, and Reconciliation intentions). Finally, they answered the demographic questions and were debriefed.

Feelings towards the outgroup were registered using Feeling thermometer (Converse & Presser, 1986). Participants indicated the valence of their feelings on a visual-analogue scale going from 0 (completely negative) to 100 (completely positive).

Social distance was measured using the Bogardus' Social distance scale. Participants were asked whether they would accept the outgroup (Bosniak / Serb) as a) co-worker, b) boss, c) close friend, d) family member, e) partner, rating each on a 7-point scale. We recoded the items and computed the mean score so that higher scores represent higher distance.

Reconciliation intentions were measured using the short scale taken from (Petrović, 2017); e.g., “We [Serbs and Bosniaks] have to forgive each other for a better future.”). We calculated the mean score of the four items.

Outgroup bias was computed as a principal component of these three measures, given their high correlation, and the p -value inflation in case of conducting the same tests on different outcomes. In both experiments, the three variables had almost equal loadings on the principal component (SOM: Section 3), indicating their equal relevance for the linear composite representing bias.

As these experiments were a part of the first author's doctoral project, additional measures were registered, but not reported here (SOM: Section 4).

Participants

Power analysis indicated that we needed at least 129 participants per condition (total $N = 387$) to detect the small interaction effects between plausibility and intervention type ($f^2 = .02$) with the power of .80 and alpha error probability of .05. In Experiment 4 (Serbia), 440

participants met the participation criteria (Serbian citizenship and ethnicity, at least 18 years old) and passed the attention and comprehension checks. In Experiment 5 (FBH) we managed to recruit $N = 348$ due to the lack of resources. Post-hoc power analysis suggested that we achieved the power of .75 with this sample size. The samples are described in Table 6.

[Table 6 here]

Analytic strategy

Analytic strategy is detailed in Table 7.

[Table 7 here]

Experiment 4: results

Descriptive statistics and intercorrelations are detailed in Appendix B, Table B4. The intercorrelations between the variables correspond to what we observed in experiments 1-3. As for the distribution of the variables, it is notable that most of the participants perceived the outgroup in a positive manner.

Manipulation check

Both Ingroup norm intervention ($t(437) = 4.301, p < .001, \text{Cohen's } d = .48$) and Outgroup experience ($t(437) = 5.707, p < .001, \text{Cohen's } d = .69$) induced the perception of GG's dual identity higher than it was in the control group.

[Table 8 here]

Hypotheses testing

We observed no significant differences between the conditions for any of the three variables tested within H6 (all $F_s < 0.650$, all $p_s > .500$), which contrasts our H6. We re-tested

the models controlling for demographic variables, ideological and intergroup beliefs, and outgroup contact, and the result was similar (all F s < .610, all p s > .544).

As for H7, we tested the interaction between intervention type and plausibility on intergroup bias (computed as a principal component). The model explained 52.3% of the variance ($F(12,427) = 41.160, p < .001, R^2 = .536, R^2_{adj} = .523$). The intervention type * plausibility interaction explained an additional 1.4% of the variance ($\Delta R^2 = .014, \Delta F(2,425) = 6.32, p = .002$). As hypothesized, interaction terms were significant, both for the differences between the two experimental conditions ($\beta = .09, p = .042$) and for the difference between Outgroup experience and control condition ($\beta = .16, p < .001$). Regression coefficients are detailed in Appendix C, Table C7. The Outgroup experience intervention successfully reduced bias when assessed as highly plausible, but backfired when assessed as implausible (Figure 6).

[Figure 6 here]

Experiment 5: results

Descriptive statistics and intercorrelations are detailed in Appendix B, Table B5. The intercorrelations between the variables correspond to what we observed in the experiment 4. Similar to Experiment 4, distribution of the variables indicated that most of the participants perceived the outgroup in a positive manner.

Manipulation check

Dual identity perception was higher after reading the Outgroup experience intervention compared to the control condition ($t(345) = 2.702, p = .007, \text{Cohen's } d = .36$). On the contrary, the Ingroup norm condition did not differ from the control in terms of GG's dual identity

perception ($t(345) = 0.947, p = .344$, Cohen's $d = .12$). Thus, in the context of FBH, only the intervention framed from the outgroup members' perspective induced the perception of the GG as dually identified, however, it was still below the theoretical midpoint of 50.

[Table 9 here]

Hypotheses testing

Consistent with the Experiment 4, we observed no significant differences between the conditions for any of the three variables tested within H6 (all F s < 1.244, all p s > .280), which contrasts our H6. As in Experiment 4, we re-run the models controlling for demographic variables, ideological and intergroup beliefs, and outgroup contact, and the result was similar (all F s < 2.184, all p s > .110).

To test H7, we ran the regression model with Experimental condition, plausibility, and their interaction serving as predictors, whilst outgroup bias (principal component) served as an outcome. The model explained 63.9% of the variance ($F(12,335) = 52.250, p < .001, R^2 = .652, R^2_{adj} = .639$). Adding the Intervention type * plausibility interaction accounted for the additional .06% of the variance ($\Delta R^2 = .006, \Delta F(2,333) = 2.69, p = .069$). Consistent to H7 and to the findings of Experiment 4, the interaction term was significant both for the difference between the two experimental interventions ($\beta = .09, p = .031$), and marginally significant for the difference between the Outgroup experience and control group ($\beta = .09, p = .072$). Regression coefficients are detailed in Appendix C, Table C8. Again, Outgroup experience intervention successfully reduced bias when assessed as highly plausible, but backfired when assessed as implausible (Figure 7).

[Figure 7 here]

General Discussion

We conducted five experiments in post-conflict contexts of Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, applying the Gateway group paradigm for intergroup bias reduction. The two intervention types were framed from either ingroup or outgroup perspectives, both signalling that gateway group members (Bosniaks in Serbia and RS, and Serbs in FBH) are equally loyal to their ethnic group (minority) and country they live in (majority). In the Outgroup experience intervention, information about dual loyalty was framed from the minority (outgroup) perspective—minority members declared themselves as strongly identified to both minority and majority. In the Ingroup norm intervention, the same information was framed from the majority (ingroup) perspective—majority members explained that they perceived the minority as loyal to both groups. First, we explored whether plausibility assessment of the two interventions is shaped by motivated reasoning, i.e., whether ideological and intergroup beliefs (ideology, ingroup identification, perspective taking, and outgroup threat perception) shape the extent to which participants assessed intervention content as plausible. Second, we tested whether plausibility assessment was related to two outcomes: dual identity perception, and intergroup bias reduction.

Motivated reasoning in plausibility assessment

We proposed that intervention plausibility assessments are shaped by motivated reasoning, such that prior beliefs and attitudes influence how individuals interpret and accept the content. Consistent with this, across all three contexts, participants higher in perspective taking and lower in perceived outgroup threat were more likely to evaluate the interventions as plausible. This is in line with previous findings regarding motivated reasoning in racial relations (Feldman & Huddy, 2018). We saw that individuals who were less willing to understand the minority perspective (lower perspective-taking) and more prejudiced against them (higher

perceived outgroup threat), were at the same time more likely to reject the content that affirms minority members' dual identity. This was observed both for the Outgroup experience intervention, that was expected to be sensitive to perspective taking and threat perception, and for the Ingroup norm one. Perspective taking and especially threat perception seem to play a significant role in judging of intervention content plausibility, even for the interventions that do not primarily rely on outgroup trust.

In the context of the methodological practices in socio-psychological experiments, that either ignore plausibility assessment, or use it as a filtering criterion (Authors, 2022a; Authors, 2022b; Kunst et al., 2019; Levy et al., 2017), our findings suggest that excluding participants who rejected the intervention content can lead to less generalizable findings. In fact, our results unambiguously imply that individuals who perceive the outgroup as threatening are more likely to reject the intervention content. Given that threat perception is a close proxy to prejudice (Stephen et al., 2015), filtering out these participants would mean excluding the most prejudiced ones, whilst mildly prejudiced and unprejudiced individuals remain in the sample. Consequently, the conclusions of such research cannot be generalized to the population since researchers cannot know how interventions affected the individuals who are strongly prejudiced.

How plausibility assessment shapes intergroup outcomes?

Across the Experiments 1-3, we observed that the more plausible participants assessed the intervention content, the stronger they perceived the GG as dually identified. Importantly, this effect was more pronounced for the Outgroup experience intervention than for the Ingroup norm one. Thus, although both interventions' plausibility was shaped by motivated reasoning, the one framed from the outgroup perspective was more sensitive to plausibility.

In Experiments 4–5, not only we replicated the finding that the Outgroup Experience intervention was more sensitive to plausibility than the Intergroup one, we observed a backfire effect among participants who judged it as implausible. Importantly, although the main effects of interventions on outgroup bias were not observed, outgroup bias decreased in certain subgroups, i.e. among those who were exposed to the Outgroup experience intervention AND assessed it as highly plausible (1SD above the average). This same intervention increased outgroup bias among those who assessed its content as implausible (1SD below the average). In other words, the effects of Outgroup experience intervention fully depended on its perceived plausibility: while it was effective if perceived plausible, it backfired if not. On the other hand, the Ingroup Norm intervention did not reduce bias, regardless of its perceived plausibility. Its null effect may reflect superficial norm learning. According to a three-stage model (Zhang et al., 2023), norm change involves detection, practice, and internalization. Our intervention likely remained at the detection stage, without enabling behavioral practice or internalization. Future research on descriptive norms in intergroup contexts should thus consider these stages and try to evoke deeper engagement.

Context specificities of the observed effects

Although the predictors of plausibility and its moderating effects were consistent across the experiments, the levels perceived plausibility varied across context. In FBH (Experiment 3), the interventions were assessed as equally plausible. On the other hand, Outgroup experience intervention was more plausible in Serbia (Experiment 1), whereas the Ingroup norm intervention was more plausible in RS (Experiment 2). These inconsistencies can be attributed to

the context-related specificities: different group status in each territory and differences in each group's role during the Bosnian war.

In Serbia (Experiment 1), Bosniaks are recognized as a constitutive ethnic minority and are constitutionally granted cultural and educational autonomy (Constitution of the Republic of Serbia). Despite the documented cases of blatant discrimination against Bosniaks (Sandžak Press, 2024), they are typically portrayed as equal citizens in the media and public discourse at large. Moreover, some prominent public figures have openly signalled their dual loyalties (to Serbian country and to Bosniak ethnic group), which might have made the Outgroup experience intervention closer to participants' everyday experience. At the same time, narratives that portray Serbs as historical victims boost prejudice, which might have made it more difficult to believe that ethnic Serbs dominantly perceive Bosniaks as having dual loyalties. In Republika Srpska (Experiment 2), however, the situation is different. RS is the entity defined exclusively through the ethnicity of the majority group (literally *Republic of Serbs*), making portraying Bosniaks as its proud citizens pretty strange. On the contrary, learning that Serbs perceive Bosniaks as such might seem less weird, leading to the higher plausibility of the Ingroup norm intervention. Finally, the absence of the between-interventions differences regarding plausibility in FBH context (Experiment 3) might have come from the existing expectations. Here, dual identity was portrayed as loyalty to ethnic Serbs (minority) and Bosnia and Herzegovina as a country. Given that Serbs from RS and FBH are expected to identify as *Bosnians* (citizens of Bosnia and Herzegovina), both ingroup and outgroup framings made sense to participants, leading to equal plausibility of the two interventions.

This, once again, highlights the importance of societal context in testing and applying intergroup interventions. We showed that even this first step - plausibility assessment of the

interventions' content - differs among the same groups in the different contexts. Accordingly, we observed the inconsistencies in correlations between plausibility assessment and a) ideology and b) ingroup identification, that seems to also be context-related. On the other hand, threat perception and perspective taking were shown as stable, context-unrelated correlates of plausibility, indicating partial uniformity in beliefs that shape plausibility assessment of intergroup interventions.

Limitations of the current research

Throughout all experiments, we tested the same set of individual differences and their relations to plausibility to allow for robust conclusions about the contextual differences between the experiments. This allowed us to show the contextual (in)consistencies regarding the relations between individual characteristics and plausibility, as well as regarding the role of plausibility in interventions' success. Future studies should examine other relevant individual and relational characteristics, such as trust (Tam et al., 2009), or intergroup meta-perceptions (Authors, 2022c).

Second, we could have merged Experiments 1-3 into a single one, with the additional factor of context; the same is true for Experiments 4-5. Even though this would allow us to compare the effects across the contexts, it would mean testing the three-way interactions (context * intervention type * plausibility). To achieve the statistical power to do so, we would need a lot larger samples (Giner-Sorolla et al., 2024; Lakens & Caldwell, 2021), which is why we planned them as separate experiments.

Third, we tested predictors of plausibility and its role in shaping interventions' effects, using the Gateway group paradigm (Levy et al., 2017) across different contexts. An alternative approach would encompass testing more paradigms in a single societal context. That would allow researchers to compare the interventions in terms of how individual beliefs shape their

plausibility, and further how plausibility shapes their effects on intergroup bias. Additionally, the variables that served as predictors of plausibility in this research (e.g., perspective taking, threat perception) could be manipulated so that their causal effects on plausibility can be tracked.

Finally, our Ingroup norm intervention failed to reduce intergroup bias, even when assessed as highly plausible. As this could be a consequence of superficial learning of new descriptive norms, to stimulate more engagement, future procedures could plan for behavioral application of the norms. Such an approach would allow us to draw firmer conclusions about the mechanism of descriptive norm acquisition in intergroup bias reduction.

Implications and recommendations for future research

The findings of our experiments are in line with the contemporary idea that tailoring intergroup interventions for a particular social group is the key for their success (Bar-Tal & Hameiri, 2020; Hameiri et al., 2016; Hebel-Sela et al., 2025; Nir & Halperin, 2025). They suggest that, to be useful and generalizable, the interventions have to be carefully tested taking into account societal context, key social and ideological characteristics of the groups in question, as well as key personality characteristics of their members.

First, we showed that contextual and individual characteristics can strongly shape plausibility of the intervention content, and that this pattern varies across interventions. Therefore, plausibility should be routinely if the interventions are sensitive to it (i.e., if it makes sense to ask participants about plausibility, believability, or credibility of intervention content), and should never be used as an exclusion criterion. Using it as such can lead to problems in scaling it and implementing it in the real-world: an intervention can be beneficial for unprejudiced individuals, but backfire among the highly prejudiced persons, which might even constitute a majority in divided societies.

Second, we demonstrated that even minor changes in context can affect the effects of interventions, and thus that generalization should not be a-priory assumed. On the contrary, the interventions should be carefully tailored to fit the local contexts, or at least to be less sensitive to motivated cognition - which has to be empirically tested across contexts.

To conclude, the observed effects are in line with the current trend of abandoning the “one intervention fits all” approach and moving towards more tailored ways of intergroup bias reduction that would take into account individual characteristics, group dynamics, and the broader societal context. (Čehajić-Clancy & Halperin, 2024; Halperin & Schori-Eyal, 2020; Landry & Halperin, 2025). Such context-sensitive rigor, rather than attempts to decontextualize, may be essential for developing high-quality interventions capable of promoting positive social change.

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Tables

Table 1

Overview of sample structure in Experiments 1-3

	Experiment 1	Experiment 2	Experiment 3
Sample size	328	387	393
Country (entity)	Serbia	Bosnia and Herzegovina (Republika Srpska)	Bosnia and Herzegovina (Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina)
Ethnicity	Serbian	Serbian	Bosniak
Age	18-77 ($M = 44.3$, $SD = 13.3$)	18-75 ($M = 33.9$, $SD = 13.3$)	18-73 ($M = 35.5$, $SD = 14.4$)
Gender	55% women, 44% men, 1% other	70% women, 29% men, 1% other	68% women, 30% men, 2% other
Recruitment type	Social media ads	Social media ads and university courses	Social media ads and university courses
Compensation	No	Course credits if recruited through university courses	Course credits if recruited through university courses
Ingroup	Serbs	Serbs	Bosniaks
Outgroup	Bosniaks	Bosniaks	Serbs

Gateway group	Bosniaks living in Serbia	Bosniaks living in Republika Srpska	Serbs living in Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina
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Table 2

Analytic strategy, Experiments 1-3

Hypothesis	Analysis	Independent variables	Dependent variables	Control variables	Moderators
H1	ANOVA with planned contrasts	Experimental condition	Plausibility	/	
H2	ANOVA with planned contrasts	Experimental condition	Dual identity perception	/	
H3	ANOVA with planned contrasts	Experimental condition	Dual identity perception	/	
H4	Pearson's correlations & linear regression	Ideology; Ingroup identification; Perspective taking; Outgroup threat	Plausibility	Gender; Age; Education; Religiosity	
H5	Pearson's correlations	Plausibility	Dual identity perception		

Exploratory	Linear regression	Experimental condition	Dual identity perception	Gender; Age; Education; Religiosity; Ideology; Ingroup identification; Perspective taking; Outgroup threat	Plausibility
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Table 3

Plausibility and dual identity perception across conditions, Experiment 1

Condition	Plausibility			Dual identity perception	
	N	M	SD	M	SD
Ingroup norm	115	4.42	1.10	55.26	23.59
Outgroup experience	99	4.78	0.95	60.87	25.13
Control	114	4.40	1.02	41.86	22.29
ANOVA model test		$F(2,325) = 4.836, p = .008, \eta^2 = .029$		$F(2,325) = 18.539, p < .001, \eta^2 = .102$	

Table 4

Plausibility and dual identity perception across conditions, Experiment 2

Condition	Plausibility			Dual identity perception	
	N	M	SD	M	SD
Ingroup norm	126	4.36	0.95	34.44	26.25
Outgroup experience	130	3.87	1.12	38.85	26.54
Control	131	3.64	1.12	29.76	25.62
ANOVA model test		$F(2,384) = 15.040, p < .001, \eta^2 = .073$		$F(2,384) = 3.948, p = .020, \eta^2 = .02$	

Table 5

Plausibility and dual identity perception across conditions, Experiment 3

Condition	Plausibility			Dual identity perception	
	N	M	SD	M	SD
Ingroup norm	126	4.40	1.00	45.68	29.67
Outgroup experience	135	3.40	0.85	47.33	23.82
Control	132	3.80	1.12	43.25	29.60
ANOVA model test		$F(2,390) = 16.040, p < .001, \eta^2 = .080$		$F(2,390) = 0.724, p = .484, \eta^2 = .00.$	

Table 6

Overview of sample structure in Experiments 4-5

	Experiment 4	Experiment 5
Sample size	440	348
Country (entity)	Serbia	Bosnia and Herzegovina (Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina)
Ethnicity	Serbian	Bosniak

Age	18-73 ($M = 33.4, SD = 14.1$)	18-76 ($M = 32.5, SD = 13.9$)
Gender	77% women, 22% men, 1% other	68% women, 32% men
Recruitment type	Social media ads and university courses	Social media ads and university courses
Compensation	Course credits if recruited through university courses	Course credits if recruited through university courses
Ingroup	Serbs	Bosniaks
Outgroup	Bosniaks	Serbs
Gateway group	Bosniaks living in Serbia	Serbs living in FBH

Table 7

Analytic strategy, Experiments 4-5

Hypothesis	Analysis	Independent variables	Dependent variables	Control variables	Moderators
Manipulation check	ANOVA with planned contrasts	Experimental condition	Dual identity perception	/	/
H6	ANOVA with planned contrasts; ANCOVA	Experimental condition	Outgroup feelings; Social	Gender; Age; Education; Religiosity;	/

			distance;	Ideology;	
			Reconciliation	Ingroup	
			intentions	identification;	
				Perspective	
				taking; Outgroup	
				threat perception	
				Gender; Age;	
				Education;	
				Religiosity;	
				Ideology;	
H7	Multiple inear regression	Experimental condition	Outgroup bias (PC)	Ingroup identification;	Plausibility
				Perspective taking; Outgroup threat perception	

Table 8
Manipulation check, Experiment 4

Condition	Dual identity perception		
	N	M	SD
Ingroup norm	152	58.6	1.85

Outgroup experience	148	62.5	1.87
Control	140	47.2	1.93
ANOVA model test		$F(2,437) = 17.528, p < .001, \eta^2 = .07$	

Table 9

Manipulation check, Experiment 5

Condition	Dual identity perception		
	N	M	SD
Ingroup norm	116	49.4	2.43
Outgroup experience	116	43.3	2.43
Control	116	40.1	2.43
ANOVA model test		$F(2,345) = 3.760, p = .024, \eta^2 = .02$	

Figure Legends

Figure 1: The societal context of the current research

Figure 2: Procedure flow, Experiments 1-3

Figure 3: Interaction between intervention type and plausibility on dual identity perception, Experiment 1

Figure 4: Interaction between intervention type and plausibility on dual identity perception, Experiment 2

Figure 5: Interaction between intervention type and plausibility on dual identity perception, Experiment 5

Figure 6: Interaction between experimental condition and plausibility on outgroup bias, Experiment 4

Figure 7: Interaction between experimental condition and plausibility on outgroup bias, Experiment 5

Figures

Figure 1: The societal context of the current research

Note. Sources of the demographic data:
Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2019;
Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2023.

Figure 2: Procedure flow, Experiments 1-3

Figure 3: Interaction between intervention type and plausibility on dual identity perception, Experiment 1

Figure 4: Interaction between intervention type and plausibility on dual identity perception, Experiment 2

Figure 5: Interaction between intervention type and plausibility on dual identity perception, Experiment 5

Figure 6: Interaction between experimental condition and plausibility on outgroup bias,

Experiment 4

Figure 7: Interaction between experimental condition and plausibility on outgroup bias,

Experiment 5

Statement of contribution

What is already known on this subject:

- Intergroup interventions are a powerful tool for reducing intergroup hostilities and bias.
- Interventions cannot be universally effective, as they should address groups' psychological needs.
- Interventions differ in their applicability in different societal contexts.

What does this study add:

- Using plausibility as filtering criteria when testing the interventions can affect the conclusions.
- Interventions' plausibility / credibility is influenced by motivated reasoning.
- In divided societies, interventions can backfire among those who assess them as implausible.